

Synthetic, spectroscopic, magnetic and hydrolytic studies on the first heterotrimetallic alkoxides of nickel(II) derived from nonalkoxo-distannate and dititanate ligands

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Abstract : Heterotrimetallic alkoxides of Ni^{II} of the type $[\{M_2(OR)_9\}Ni\{M'_x(OR')_y\}]$ (where M = Ti^{IV}, Sn^{IV}; M' = Sn (x = 2, y = 9), Zr (x = 2, y = 9), Nb (x = 1, y = 6), Al (x = 1, y = 4); R = Prⁱ, Et, R' = Prⁱ (mainly), Et) have been prepared by salt elimination reactions involving interactions of $[\{M_2(OR)_9\}Ni(\mu-Cl)]_2$ (M = Ti^{IV}, Sn^{IV}; R = Prⁱ, Et) with two equivalents of a variety of potassium alkoxometallates, such as KZr₂(OPrⁱ)₉, KNb(OPrⁱ)₆, and KAl(OR)₄ (R = Prⁱ, Et) in benzene. Alcoholysis (with methyl alcohol and *tert*-butyl alcohol) and hydrolytic (with powdery Ba(OH)₂·8H₂O) reactions of a few typical derivatives have also been carried out. The new complexes are highly moisture-sensitive, coloured solids or viscous products. All of these have been characterized by elemental analyses, spectroscopic (IR and visible), magnetic studies as well as by molecular weight measurements. The latter studies depict monomeric nature of the new complexes.

Keywords : Nickel(II) alkoxide, heterotrimetallic alkoxides, nonaalkoxodistannates, nonaalkoxodititanates.

Introduction

Alkoxometallate ligands, such as $\{Zr_2OPr^i\}_9^-$, $\{Nb(OPr^i)_6\}_6^-$, and $\{Al(OPr^i)_4\}_4^-$, play an important role in inorganic chemistry as they easily and effectively bind a large number of metal ions of the periodic table with wide variation in cationic charges and ionic radii to form hydrocarbon soluble, stable and generally volatile heterometallic complexes^{1,2}. The development of the field of materials science during the past two decades has increased enormously the interest in heterometallic alkoxide coordination complexes¹⁻³, due to their unique physico-chemical properties and functions.

To our best of knowledge heterotrimetallic complexes of Ni^{II} featuring $\{Sn_2(OR)_9\}_9^-$ and/or $\{Ti_2(OR)_9\}_9^-$ (R = Prⁱ, Et) ligands are unknown⁴. Furthermore, investigations on metal complexes featuring these two ligands are of considerable interest because, the opportunity is provided to examine (i) the ligating behaviour of these two ligands toward divalent later 3d transition metals such as cobalt and nickel, (ii) the possibility of synthesizing

heterotrimetallic alkoxides containing two early *d*⁰ transition metals (Ti⁴⁺, Zr⁴⁺) of the same group of the periodic table, (iii) the possibility of the formation of heterotetrametallic oxide systems by incorporating barium, and (iv) the relative stability of the metal complexes of $\{Sn_2(OR)_9\}_9^-$ and $\{Ti_2(OR)_9\}_9^-$ ligands. The comparable ionic sizes⁵ of Sn⁴⁺ (0.69 Å) and Ti⁴⁺ (0.61 Å) in coordination number six, suggests that their complexes should be similar in stability, reactivity and structural features. However, distinct differences are also noted in the cases of Ti(OPrⁱ)₄ and Sn(OPrⁱ)₄, the latter is trimeric whereas former is monomeric.

Keeping above view points in mind, we report in this paper for the first time the synthesis, spectroscopic and magnetic properties, alcoholysis and hydrolytic reactions of heterotrimetallic alkoxides of Ni^{II} containing $\{Sn_2(OR)_9\}_9^-$ and/or $\{Ti_2(OR)_9\}_9^-$ as coordinating ligands. We anticipate that this paper will stimulate researchers working in diverse areas such as synthetic metal-organic chemistry, catalysis and materials science.

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Experimental

In view of the highly moisture-sensitive nature of homo- and heterometallic alkoxides, all reactions and manipulations were performed under rigorous anhydrous conditions. Therefore, for eliminating as far as possible any moisture which might arise from apparatus, chemicals, or air; all preparative reactions were performed in glass apparatus fitted with standard quick fit interchangeable joints (B₁₄, B₁₉, B₂₄ cones and sockets) and protected from moisture by placing guard tubes filled with silica-gel impregnated with a coloured moisture indicator at appropriate places. In alcoholysis experiments, fractionations were carried out by using a column (60 cm) packed with Raschig rings and fitted to a total condensation variable take-off still-head, the latter being fitted with a thermometer pocket and a stop cock; silica-gel filled guard-tubes were placed at appropriate points. Prior to use all glass apparatus were carefully washed, rinsed with ethyl alcohol, and oven dried at 130–140 °C for ~2 h and cooled either in a desiccator or were assembled hot, suitably protected with guard- or side-tubes filled with silica-gel. Reagent grade solvents were dried by refluxing over convenient drying agents and distilled prior to use⁶. Anhydrous NiCl₂ was prepared from NiCl₂·6H₂O by the thionyl chloride method⁷.

Homometal alkoxides : Ti(OR)₄ (R = Prⁱ, Et), Zr(OPrⁱ)₄, PrⁱOH, Nb(OPrⁱ)₅, Al(OR)₃ (R = Prⁱ, Et); heterobimetallic alkoxides : KSn₂(OPrⁱ)₉, KSn₂(OEt)₉, KTi₂(OPrⁱ)₉, KTi₂(OEt)₉, KZr₂(OPrⁱ)₆, KNb(OPrⁱ)₆, KAl(OPrⁱ)₄ and KAl(OEt)₄ were prepared by literature methods². The precursor chloro-derivatives [Ni{M₂(OR)₉}(μ-Cl)]₂ (M = Ti, Sn; R = Et, Prⁱ) were prepared according to the procedure recently described by us⁴.

In heterometallic derivatives titanium, zirconium, tin, niobium, aluminium, and nickel were determined gravimetrically as TiO₂, ZrO₂, SnO₂, Nb₂O₅, oxinate, and as dimethylglyoximate, respectively⁸. Isopropoxy or ethoxy groups in the new complexes were determined by the oxidimetric method⁹. In order to achieve a complete quantitative separation and determination of the metals present in mixed-metal oxides, freshly prepared by low temperature pyrolysis, special procedures such as given below were followed :

(i) Estimation of Ba, Ni, Ti and Zr in hetrotetrametallic oxide :

Titanium was separated as titanic acid by digestion, the weighed amount of mixed-metal oxide with 15 cm³ of concentrated nitric acid on a low temperature hot plate, followed by addition of 50 cm³ of water and stirring for ~5 min. The precipitated titanic acid was filtered, washed, and finally converted to TiO₂, and weighed as such.

The filtrate obtained after removal of titanium as titanic acid was reduced in volume to ~10 cm³ and 5-cm³ of concentrated sulphuric acid was added. The solution was then evaporated carefully on a low temperature hot plate until white fumes were evolved. The pasty mass was allowed to cool and then 5 cm³ of concentrated hydrochloric acid, along with 50 cm³ of water added, stirred, filtered through gravimetric filter paper, washed with water, carefully ignited, and weighed as barium sulphate.

The combined filtrate and washings obtained after removal of barium sulfate was evaporated to 50 cm³ and then 20 cm³ of concentrated hydrochloric acid was added. The zirconium was precipitated as zirconium mandelate. The precipitate was filtered off, washed with a hot solution containing 2% HCl and 5% mandelic acid and weighed in the form of ZrO₂ after ignition.

After evaporation of the combined filtrate and washings (obtained after removal of zirconium) to 50 cm³, was added 25 cm³ of concentrated nitric acid and 15 cm³ of concentrated hydrochloric acid and then evaporated the solution nearly to dryness, in order to destroy excess mandelic acid. The residual mass was dissolved by adding 1 cm³ of concentrated hydrochloric acid and 100 cm³ of water. To this solution 1 : 1 ammonia solution was added until slightly ammonical. The nickel was precipitated by the addition of an alcoholic solution of dimethylglyoxime. The precipitate was washed with cold water and then weighed as nickel bis(dimethylglyoximate) after drying at 110–120 °C.

(ii) Estimation of Ni, Ti and Zr in hetrotrimetallic oxide :

The procedure described above is applicable for quantitative separation and estimation of Ti, Zr and Ni in the similar sequence.

(iii) Estimation of Ni and Zr in heterobimetallic oxide :

Accurately weighed sample of mixed-metal oxide was dissolved in hot concentrated sulphuric acid (15 cm³).

After addition of 50 cm³ water, the clear solution was evaporated until white fumes evolved. The solution was diluted with water to ~50 cm³ and then added 20 cm³ concentrated hydrochloric acid. The zirconium was precipitated as zirconium mandelate and after usual work-up weighed in the form of ZrO₂.

The filtrate obtained after removal of zirconium was evaporated to reduce the volume to ~10 cm³. After addition of 15 cm³ concentrated nitric acid, the solution was evaporated on a hot plate to destroy excess of mandelic acid. The residual mass was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and diluted with water to ~50 cm³. To this solution 1 : 1 ammonia solution was added until slightly ammoniacal. From this solution, after usual work-up nickel was determined as nickel bis(dimethylglyoximate).

(iv) *Estimation of Sn and Ni heterobimetallic oxide :*

By digesting mixed-metal oxide with 15 cm³ concentrated nitric acid, followed by addition of 50 cm³ water and constant stirring, tin was separated as stannic acid. The residue was filtered, washed, converted to SnO₂ by ignition, and weighed as such.

The filtrate and washings obtained after separation of stannic acid was used for the determination of nickel by the procedure described earlier.

By subtracting sum of the percentages of constituent metals from that of 100, the percentage of oxygen or OH group in the mixed-metal oxides can be tentatively calculated.

IR spectra (4000–400 cm⁻¹) were recorded on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT-IR spectrophotometer in Nujol mulls or as KBr pellet using CsI optics. Electronic spectra were recorded in different solvents using quartz optics on a Cary 50 Bio-Ultra violet-visible spectrophotometer. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were made by the Gouy method on a Polytronic Gouy balance (EMP-75) using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as a calibrant. Molecular weights were determined ebullioscopically in benzene solution using a Gallenkamp ebulliometer employing a thermister sensing device.

Synthesis of heterotrimetallic alkoxides :

(i) [*Al(OPrⁱ)₄*]*Ni*{*Sn₂(OPrⁱ)₉*} (10) : To a benzene (50 cm³) solution of [*Ni*{*Sn₂(OPrⁱ)₉*}(*μ-Cl*)₂] (2.52 g, 1.46 mmol) was added a suspension of *KAl(OPrⁱ)₄* {prepared by reacting potassium metal (0.11 g, 2.94 mgatom) with

isopropyl alcohol (10 cm³) in the presence of *Al(OPrⁱ)₃* (0.60 g, 2.94 mmol) in benzene (25 cm³) under refluxing conditions, followed by removal of the volatiles} in benzene (25 cm³). After intimate mixing of the two reactants, colour of the reaction mixture changed from violet to blue. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for ~10 h, followed by refluxing for an additional period of 4 h, during which colour changed from blue to reddish-blue. The precipitated *KCl* (0.22 g, 2.95 mmol) was removed by filtration. Volatiles from the filtrate were removed under reduced pressure to obtain the title compound (10) as a reddish-blue crystalline solid (3.00 g, 94%). The compound was recrystallized from *n*-hexane at -20 °C in 2.57 g (81%) yield. A procedure similar to that of (10) was adopted to prepare other heterotrimetallic alkoxides of nickel(II) (1)-(9) and (11)-(16) from appropriate reactants in desired stoichiometry.

Reaction of [*Zr₂(OPrⁱ)₉*]*Ni*{*Ti₂(OPrⁱ)₉*} (3) *with an excess of methyl alcohol* : On addition of an excess of methyl alcohol (50 cm³) to the solution of [*Zr₂(OPrⁱ)₉*]*Ni*{*Ti₂(OPrⁱ)₉*} (3) (2.20 g, 1.57 mmol) in benzene (25 cm³), slight heat was evolved and colour changed from purple to greenish-yellow. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 15 h, followed by refluxing for 2 h, whereupon insoluble light yellow solid was precipitated, which was removed by filtration and dried under reduced pressure to obtain light yellow solid of composition [*Zr₂(OMe)₉*]*Ni*{*Ti₂(OMe)₉*} (17) in 1.20 g (86%) yield.

(ii) *Reaction of* [*Sn₂(OPrⁱ)₉*]*Ni*{*Ti₂(OPrⁱ)₉*} (1) *with excess Bu^tOH* : To a benzene (~20 cm³) solution of [*Sn₂(OPrⁱ)₉*]*Ni*{*Ti₂(OPrⁱ)₉*} (1) (2.57 g, 1.76 mmol) was added an excess of *tert*-butyl alcohol (~60 cm³). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 30 h, with continuous azeotropic removal of the liberated isopropyl alcohol which was collected and estimated. When required amount of isopropyl alcohol has been collected in the azeotrope and further collected azeotrope did not show the presence of an oxidizable species, the refluxing was stopped and solution was allowed to cool to room temperature. The volatiles from the solution were removed under reduced pressure to afford violet-red viscous mass 2.81 g (98%). The viscous material was dissolved in a 1 : 6 mixture of toluene-*n*-hexane and the solution was kept at -20 °C for

3 days to obtain violet-red product in 2.73 g (95% yield). Analysis of the compound corresponded to the composition $[\{\text{Sn}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_3(\text{OBu}^t)_6\}\text{Ni}\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_3(\text{OBu}^t)_6\}]$ (**18**).

By adopting procedure similar to that described above, the reaction of $[\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\}\text{Ni}\{\text{Sn}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}]$ (**10**) (2.00 g, 1.83 mmol) with excess *tert*-butyl alcohol ($\sim 50 \text{ cm}^3$) afforded purple pasty solid 2.19 g (99%) of composition $[\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_2(\text{OBu}^t)_2\}\text{Ni}\{\text{Sn}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_3(\text{OBu}^t)_6\}]$ (**19**), which was recrystallized from 6 : 1 mixture of *n*-hexane-toluene at -20°C in 2.10 g (95% yield).

Hydrolytic reactions :

(i) *Reaction of $[\{\text{Zr}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}\text{Ni}\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}]$ (**3**) with water* : To a clear solution of $[\{\text{Zr}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}\text{Ni}\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}]$ (**3**) (1.86 g, 1.33 mmol) in isopropyl alcohol ($\sim 30 \text{ cm}^3$) water was added dropwise (0.45 g, 24.42 mmol) dissolved in Pr^iOH ($\sim 10 \text{ cm}^3$). After stirring at room temperature for ~ 15 h, light yellow gelatinuous product was formed. Excess solvent and volatiles were removed under reduced pressure to obtain light yellow solid of composition $[\text{NiTi}_2\text{Zr}_2(\text{OH})_{18}]$ (**A**) (0.82 g, 96%) (Found : Ni, 9.10; Ti, 14.81; Zr, 28.35. Calcd. for $[\text{NiTi}_2\text{Zr}_2(\text{OH})_{18}]$ (**A**) : Ni, 9.13; Ti, 14.89; Zr, 28.37%). The presence of OH groups in compound (**A**) was confirmed by the appearance of a broad absorption band at 3320 cm^{-1} . On heating the compound (**A**) for 3 h upto 300°C in silica crucible yielded greenish-yellow solid of composition $[\text{NiTi}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_9]$ (**B**) (0.55 g, 90%) (Found : Ni, 12.17; Ti, 19.85; Zr, 37.99. Calcd. for $[\text{NiTi}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_9]$ (**B**) : Ni, 12.20; Ti, 19.91; Zr, 37.94%). The compound (**B**) showed disappearance of absorption band due to $\nu(\text{OH})$ groups.

(ii) *Reaction of $[\{\text{Zr}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}\text{Ni}\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}]$ (**3**) with $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 1 : 1 molar ratio* :

To the solution of $[\{\text{Zr}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}\text{Ni}\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}]$ (**3**) (1.80 g, 1.28 mmol) in isopropyl alcohol ($\sim 50 \text{ cm}^3$) powdered $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.41 g, 1.30 mmol) in 1 : 1 molar ratio was added. After stirring at room temperature for ~ 10 h, brownish-yellow turbid solution was obtained, which changed to gelatinuous product on further stirring the reaction mixture for a period of 6 h. The removal of the solvent and volatiles under reduced pressure yielded light-yellow solid of composition $[\text{BaNiTi}_2\text{Zr}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_{10}(\text{OH})_{10}]$ (**C**) (1.48 g, 93%) (Found : Ba, 11.06; Ni, 4.71; Ti, 7.63; Zr, 14.68; (OPr^i) , 47.73. Calcd. for $[\text{BaNiTi}_2\text{Zr}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_{10}(\text{OH})_{10}]$ (**C**) : Ba, 11.12;

Ni, 4.75; Ti, 7.75; Zr, 14.77; (OPr^i) , 47.84%). The presence of OH and isopropoxo groups in the compound (**C**) was confirmed by the appearance of absorption bands at 3332 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{OH})$, 1135–1165 due to $\nu(\text{OPr}^i)$ and at $1050\text{--}1100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu(\text{C--O})$. The compound (**C**) was heated for 2 h upto 300°C in a silica crucible to yield greenish-yellow solid of composition $[\text{BaNiTi}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_{10}]$ (**D**) (0.71 g, 93%) (Found : Ba, 21.59; Ni, 9.20; Ti, 15.01; Zr, 28.72. Calcd. for $[\text{BaNiTi}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_{10}]$ (**D**) : Ba, 21.65; Ni, 9.25; Ti, 15.10; Zr, 28.77%). The absorptions due to $\nu(\text{OH})$ and $\nu(\text{OPr}^i)$ were absent in compound (**D**).

(iii) *Reaction of compound (**3**) with $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 1 : 3 molar ratio* :

After addition of $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ powder (1.55 g, 1.11 mmol) to a solution of $[\{\text{Zr}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}\text{Ni}\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}]$ (**3**) (2.29 g, 1.63 mmol) in isopropyl alcohol (50 cm^3), the reaction mixture was vigorously stirred at room temperature for 10 h, and then refluxed for 7 h. The resulting gel type reaction mixture was then allowed to cool to room temperature. Excess solvent and volatile matters were removed under reduced pressure to obtain the yellow product $[\text{Ba}_3\text{NiTi}_2\text{Zr}_2(\text{OH})_{24}]$ (**E**) (1.74 g, 92%) (Found : Ba, 35.52; Ni, 5.00; Ti, 8.15; Zr, 15.68. Calcd. for $[\text{Ba}_3\text{NiTi}_2\text{Zr}_2(\text{OH})_{24}]$ (**E**) : Ba, 35.61; Ni, 5.07; Ti, 8.28; Zr, 15.77%). The presence of OH groups in the compound (**E**) was confirmed by the appearance of broad absorption band at 3340 cm^{-1} . Hydroxo product (**E**) on heating for 2 h at 300°C yielded heterotetrametallic oxide of composition $[\text{Ba}_3\text{NiTi}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_{12}]$ (**F**) (1.28 g, 91%) (Found : Ba, 43.70; Ni, 6.18; Ti, 10.00; Zr, 19.31. Calcd. for $[\text{Ba}_3\text{NiTi}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_{12}]$ (**F**) : Ba, 43.79; Ni, 6.24; Ti, 10.18; Zr, 19.39%).

Action of heat under reduced pressure : The nickel complexes $[\{\text{Sn}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}\text{Ni}\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}]$ (**1**) (1.50 g) and $[\{\text{Zr}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}\text{Ni}\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}]$ (**3**) (2.90 g) on being heated upto 300°C under reduced pressure (0.1 mm Hg) disproportionated into volatile and nonvolatile components, which were also collected, weighed, and analysed in each case.

Volatile component (0.57 g) for compound (**1**) (Found : Ti, 16.80; (OPr^i) , 83.05. Calcd. for $[\text{Ti}(\text{OPr}^i)_4]$: Ti, 16.84; (OPr^i) , 83.05%). Nonvolatile component (0.41 g) (Found

Ni, 13.86; Sn, 55.86; (OPrⁱ), 13.81. Calcd. for [NiSn₂O_{4.5}(OPrⁱ)] : Ni, 13.74; Sn, 55.57; (OPrⁱ), 13.81%.

Volatile component (1.15 g) for compound (3) (Found : Ti, 16.73; (OPrⁱ), 83.10. Calcd. for [Ti(OPrⁱ)₄] : Ti, 16.84; (OPrⁱ), 83.15%). Nonvolatile component (0.86 g) (Found Ni, 13.97; Zr, 43.29; (OPrⁱ), 27.84. Calcd. for [NiZr₂O₄(OPrⁱ)₂] : Ni, 13.86; Zr, 43.10; (OPrⁱ), 27.92%).

Results and discussion

Heterotrimetallic alkoxide coordination complexes of nickel(II) have been synthesized by the reactions of dimeric precursor chloro-derivatives [{M₂(OR)₉}Ni(μ-Cl)]₂ (M = Ti, Sn) with two equivalents of a variety of potassium alkoxometallates in benzene medium.

	M	R	M'	R'	x	y
1	Ti	Pr ⁱ	Sn	Pr ⁱ	2	9
2	Ti	Et	Sn	Et	2	9
3	Ti	Pr ⁱ	Zr	Pr ⁱ	2	9
4	Ti	Et	Zr	Pr ⁱ	2	9
5	Sn	Pr ⁱ	Zr	Pr ⁱ	2	9
6	Sn	Et	Zr	Pr ⁱ	2	9
7	Ti	Pr ⁱ	Al	Pr ⁱ	1	4
8	Ti	Et	Al	Pr ⁱ	1	4
9	Ti	Et	Al	Et	1	4
10	Sn	Pr ⁱ	Al	Pr ⁱ	1	4
11	Sn	Et	Al	Pr ⁱ	1	4
12	Sn	Et	Al	Et	1	4
13	Ti	Pr ⁱ	Nb	Pr ⁱ	1	6
14	Ti	Et	Nb	Pr ⁱ	1	6
15	Sn	Pr ⁱ	Nb	Pr ⁱ	1	6
16	Sn	Et	Nb	Pr ⁱ	1	6

All of these derivatives are highly moisture-sensitive, coloured solids or viscous products, soluble in common organic solvents such as benzene, chloroform, and tetrahydrofuran and depict monomeric nature cryoscopically/ebullioscopically in benzene.

Reaction of [{Zr₂(OPrⁱ)₉}Ni{Ti₂(OPrⁱ)₉}] (3) with an excess of methyl alcohol (50 cm³) at room temperature affords methoxy analogue as an insoluble light-yellow solid (17). The structure of which is regarded to involve tridentate ligating mode of both nonamethoxodimethylate ligands, resulting in an octahedral environments of methoxy groups around nickel(II).

It is interesting, and puzzling, to see that the derivative (17) is insoluble. It appears that structural compactness arising from smallness of methoxy group may be responsible for some sort of intermolecular attraction in the solid state, but the exact reason is not readily apparent.

Reactions of [{Sn₂(OPrⁱ)₉}Ni{(OPrⁱ)₉}] (1) and [{Al(OPrⁱ)₄}Ni{Sn₂(OPrⁱ)₉}] (10) with an excess of *tert*-butyl alcohol even under refluxing conditions with continuous azeotropic fractionation of the liberated isopropyl alcohol over a period of ~30 h, yield only mixed isopropoxide-*tert*-butoxide derivatives according to following reactions [eqs. (1) and (2)].

The hydrolytic reaction of [{Zr₂(OPrⁱ)₉}Ni{Ti₂(OPrⁱ)₉}] (9) with water in 1 : 18 molar ratio in isopropyl alcohols yields a gelatinous product of composition [NiTi₂Zr₂(OH)₁₈] (A), which on heating at 300 °C for 2 h under reduced pressure produced greenish-yellow product of composition [NiTi₂Zr₂O₉] (B) (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

In an attempt to introduce barium in a heterotrimetallic system and to obtain heterotetrametallic hydroxo species and finally a heterotetrametallic oxide, the reaction of $\{Zr_2(OPr^i)_9\}Ni\{Ti_2(OPr^i)_9\}$ (3) with $Ba(OH)_2 \cdot 8H_2O$ powder in 1 : 1 and 1 : 3 molar ratios in isopropyl alcohol were carried out under different experimental conditions as illustrated in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

The above reactions assume importance because addition of $Ba(OH)_2 \cdot 8H_2O$ to the complex $\{Zr_2(OPr^i)_9\}Ni\{Ti_2(OPr^i)_9\}$ (3) in isopropyl alcohol leads to the hydrolysis with water of crystallization of $Ba(OH)_2 \cdot 8H_2O$. In this case since the crystallization water is believed to be supplied to the alkoxide solution gradually an inhomogenous precipitation resulting from rapid hydrolysis is inhibited. Furthermore, barium cations are incorporated into nickel, titanium, zirconium system, finally re-

sulting in the formation of heterotetrametallic oxide.

Attempted volatilization : When complexes (1) and (3) were attempted to volatilize under reduced pressure, they tend to disproportionate into a volatile component $[Ti(OPr^i)_4]$ and a nonvolatile species as illustrated by the following eqs. (3)–(4) :

Infrared spectral studies : The new complexes exhibit structurally important^{2,10,11} infrared absorptions in the regions (cm^{-1}) : 1110–1170 $\nu(OPr^i)$, 1100–1160 $\nu(OEt)$, 900–1090 $\nu(C-O)$, 670–685 $\nu(Al-O)$, 585–600 $\nu(Sn-O)$, 540–570 $\nu(Ti-O)$, 520–530 $\nu(Zr-O)$, 515–525 $\nu(Nb-O)$ and 420–480 $\nu(Ni-O)$. The absorption due to $\nu(OBu^i)$ groups appeared in the region 1215–1250 cm^{-1} .

Electronic spectral studies : The visible spectra of complexes (1) to (16), (18) and (19) (Table 2) consist of two intense band maxima in the 12048–13605 cm^{-1} and 23255–25000 cm^{-1} regions, which may be assigned^{11–14} to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \xrightarrow{\nu_2} {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \xrightarrow{\nu_3} {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, respectively for the octahedral nickel(II) species. In addition to the above transitions, the complexes (1), (3), (5), (7), (10), (13), (15), (18) and (19) also exhibit a doublet in the 16949–19305 cm^{-1} region due to ${}^3T_1(F) \xrightarrow{\nu'_3} {}^3T_1(P)$ transition for tetrahedral Ni^{II} species^{13,14}. The electronic spectra (Table 2) of derivatives (1), (3), and (5) show some proportion of tetrahedral nickel(II) species in equilibrium with octahedral forms¹³, which can be easily explained on the basis of structural formulations (I) and (II) involving tri(η^3)- and bi(η^2)-dentate connectivity features of nonaisopropoxodi-metallate ligands :

Furthermore, derivatives (7), (10), (13) and (15) bearing nonisopropoxodimetallate and tetraisopropoxo-

Table 1. Preparative, analytical and some physical properties of heterotrimetallic alkoxides of nickel(II)

Product (Empirical formula) Yield : g (%), Colour and state ^a	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				Mol. Wt. Found (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} (BM)
	Ni	Ti/Sn	Al/Zr	OPr ⁱ /OEt		
[[Sn ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₉]{Ni{Ti ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₉ }} (1) (C ₅₄ H ₁₂₆ O ₁₈ NiSn ₂ Ti ₂) 3.10 (77); Purple	3.90 (4.03)	22.77 ^b (22.89)	- (13.03)	72.90 (73.07)	1470 (1455)	3.58
[[Sn ₂ (OEt) ₉]{Ni{Ti ₂ (OEt) ₉ }} (2) (C ₃₆ H ₉₀ O ₁₈ NiSn ₂ Ti ₂) 2.50 (84); Reddish-yellow	4.77 (4.88)	27.50 ^b (27.69)	- (13.03)	67.34 (67.42)	1200 (1203)	3.30
[[Zr ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₉]{Ni{Ti ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₉ }} (3) (C ₅₄ H ₁₂₆ O ₁₈ NiTi ₂ Zr ₂) 1.72 (77); Purple	4.00 (4.19)	6.66 (6.84)	12.84 (13.03)	75.77 (75.94)	1415 (1400)	3.52
[[{Zr ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₉]{Ni{Ti ₂ (OEt) ₉ }}] (4) (C ₄₅ H ₁₀₈ O ₁₈ NiTi ₂ Zr ₂) 3.90 (82); Reddish-blue	4.41 (4.61)	7.28 (7.52)	13.94 (14.32)	- (12.89)	1290 (1274)	3.23
[[{Zr ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₉]{Ni{Sn ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₉ }}] (5) (C ₅₄ H ₁₂₆ O ₁₈ NiSn ₂ Zr ₂) 2.84 (82); Dark blue	3.73 (3.81)	15.18 (15.39)	11.72 (11.83)	68.81 (68.97)	1555 (1542)	3.51
[[{Zr ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₉]{Ni{Sn ₂ (OEt) ₉ }}] (6) (C ₄₅ H ₁₀₈ O ₁₈ NiSn ₂ Zr ₂) 2.32 (90); Purple	4.00 (4.14)	16.58 (16.76)	12.78 (12.89)	- (12.89)	1430 (1416)	3.25
[[Al(OPr ⁱ) ₄]{Ni{Ti ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₉ }}] (7) (C ₃₉ H ₉₁ O ₁₃ NiTi ₂ Al) 1.71 (88); Purple	6.02 (6.18)	9.93 (10.08)	2.76 (2.84)	80.71 (80.88)	967 (950)	3.44
[[Al(OPr ⁱ) ₄]{Ni{Ti ₂ (OEt) ₉ }}] (8) (C ₃₀ H ₇₃ O ₁₃ NiTi ₂ Al) 2.00 (83); Dark yellow	6.97 (7.13)	11.46 (11.63)	3.14 (3.28)	- (12.89)	830 (823)	3.08
[[Al(OEt) ₄]{Ni{Ti ₂ (OEt) ₉ }}] (9) (C ₂₆ H ₆₅ O ₁₃ NiTi ₂ Al) 2.15 (94); Yellow	7.58 (7.65)	12.22 (12.48)	3.41 (3.52)	76.17 (76.34)	781 (767)	3.11
[[Al(OPr ⁱ) ₄]{Ni{Sn ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₉ }}] (10) (C ₃₉ H ₉₁ O ₁₃ NiSn ₂ Al) 2.57 (81); Reddish-blue	5.18 (5.38)	21.47 (21.76)	2.37 (2.47)	70.18 (70.39)	1102 (1091)	3.41
[[Al(OPr ⁱ) ₄]{Ni{Sn ₂ (OEt) ₉ }}] (11) (C ₃₀ H ₇₃ O ₁₃ NiSn ₂ Al) 1.64 (78); Yellow	5.97 (6.08)	24.36 (24.60)	2.67 (2.80)	- (12.89)	980 (965)	3.03
[[Al(OEt) ₄]{Ni{Sn ₂ (OEt) ₉ }}] (12) (C ₂₆ H ₆₅ O ₁₃ NiSn ₂ Al) 1.73 (93) : Yellowish-brown	6.43 (6.46)	25.84 (26.12)	2.91 (2.97)	64.30 (64.40)	925 (909)	3.10
[[Nb(OPr ⁱ) ₆]{Ni{Ti ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₉ }}] (13) (C ₄₅ H ₁₀₅ O ₁₅ NiTi ₂ Nb) 2.61 (80); Violet	5.10 (5.18)	16.60 ^b (16.64)	- (13.03)	78.09 (78.20)	1146 (1134)	3.54
[[Nb(OPr ⁱ) ₆]{Ni{Ti ₂ (OEt) ₉ }}] (14) (C ₃₆ H ₈₇ O ₁₅ NiTi ₂ Nb) 2.00 (79); Reddish-blue	5.70 (5.82)	18.76 ^b (18.73)	- (13.03)	- (12.89)	1020 (1007)	3.15

Table-1 (contd.)

$[\{\text{Nb}(\text{OPr}^i)_6\}\text{Ni}\{\text{Sn}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}]$ (15)	4.46	25.76 ^b	-	69.36	1292	3.53
(C ₄₅ H ₁₀₅ O ₁₅ NiSn ₂ Nb)	(4.60)	(25.90)		(69.50)	(1275)	
1.88 (84); Purple						
$[\{\text{Nb}(\text{OPr}^i)_6\}\text{Ni}\{\text{Sn}_2(\text{OEt})_9\}]$ (16)	5.02	28.71 ^b	-	-	1160	3.18
(C ₃₆ H ₈₇ O ₁₅ NiSn ₂ Nb)	(5.11)	(28.74)			(1149)	
2.32 (90); Violet						
$[\{\text{Zr}_2(\text{OMe})_9\}\text{Ni}\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OMe})_9\}]$ (17)	6.50	10.53	20.30	-	-	3.04
(C ₁₈ H ₅₄ O ₁₈ NiTi ₂ Zr ₂)	(6.55)	(10.69)	(20.37)			
1.20 (86); Light-yellow						
$[\{\text{Sn}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_3(\text{OBu}^t)_6\}\text{Ni}\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_3(\text{OBu}^t)_6\}]$ (18)	3.58	20.48 ^b	-	21.79	1635	3.59
(C ₆₆ H ₁₅₀ O ₁₈ NiTi ₂ Sn ₂)	(3.61)	(20.52)		(21.83)	(1624)	
2.73 (95); Violet-red						
$[\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_2(\text{OBu}^t)_2\}\text{Ni}\{\text{Sn}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_3(\text{OBu}^t)_6\}]$ (19)	4.81	19.62	2.19	24.48	1220	3.42
(C ₄₇ H ₁₀₇ O ₁₃ NiSn ₂ Al)	(4.88)	(19.73)	(2.24)	(24.55)	(1204)	
2.10 (95); Purple						

^aCompounds (1), (3), (7), (13), (14), and (18) are viscous masses and compounds (2), (4), (8), (9), (19) are pasty solids, whereas other compounds are solids. ^bDetermined as mixed oxide.

aluminate or hexaisopropoxoniobate ligands also exist in solution in an equilibrium between octahedral and tetrahedral forms (III) and (IV) :

When the spectra of (1), (3), (5), (7), (10), (13) and (15) were recorded in isopropyl alcohol, spectral patterns remain almost the same. However, on recording the spectra in stronger coordinating solvents such as THF or pyridine (designated as L), the octahedral form becomes predominant¹³ owing to the formation of bis-adducts and possibly adopting structures of types $[\{\eta^2\text{-M}'_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}\text{-Ni}\{\eta^2\text{-M}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}(\text{L})_2]$, where L = THF or pyridine; (1) : M = Ti, M' = Sn; (3) : M = Ti, M' = Zr; (5) : M = Sn, M' = Zr and $[\{(\text{Pr}^i\text{O})_n\text{M}'(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\}\text{Ni}\{\eta^2\text{-M}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}(\text{L})_2]$, where L = THF or pyridine; (7) : M = Ti, M' = Al (n = 2); (10) : M = Sn, M' = Al (n = 2); (13) : M = Ti, M' = Nb (n = 4); (15) : M = Sn, M' = Nb (n = 4).

By contrast, the electronic spectra of ethoxy or ethoxy-isopropoxy derivatives (2), (4), (6), (8), (9), (11), (12), (14), and (16) bands in the 12804–13850 and 23256–24876

cm⁻¹ regions due to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \xrightarrow{V_2} {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \xrightarrow{V_3} {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, respectively. These results

support exclusively the presence of an octahedral geometry around Ni^{II} ion in these systems (V) and (VI) :

(2) : M = Ti, R = Et, M' = Sn, R' = Et; (4) : M = Ti, R = Et, M' = Zr, R' = Prⁱ; (6) : M = Sn, R = Et, M' = Zr, R' = Prⁱ

(8) : M = Ti, M' = Al, R' = Prⁱ, n = 2; (9) : M = Ti, M' = Al, R' = Et, n = 2; (11) : M = Sn, M' = Al, R' = Prⁱ, n = 2; (12) : M = Sn, M' = Al, R' = Et, n = 2, (14) : M = Ti, M' = Nb, R' = Prⁱ, n = 4; (16) : M = Sn, M' = Nb, R' = Prⁱ, n = 4

Magnetic studies : The room temperature magnetic moment data (Table 1) for the complexes (1)-(19) lie in the range 3.03–3.59 BM, which is expected^{14,15} for high-spin nickel(II) octahedral complexes. For all these complexes magnetic moments are slightly higher than spin only values possibly due to orbital contributions and geometrical distortion¹⁴.

Comments : The implication of the above electronic and magnetic data, together with literature precedents regarding heterometallic alkoxides of nickel(II) of the types $[\text{Ni}\{\text{Zr}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}_2]$ ¹⁶, $[\text{Ni}\{\text{M}(\text{OPr}^i)_6\}_2]$ (M = Nb, Ta)¹⁷, $[\text{Ni}\{\text{Al}(\text{OR})_4\}_2]$ ¹³, $[\{\text{Zr}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}\text{Ni}\{\text{Nb}(\text{OPr}^i)_6\}]$ ^{11a}, and

Table 2. Electronic spectral (cm^{-1}), molar extinction coefficient ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) data for heterotrimetallic alkoxides of nickel(II)

Compd.	Solvent	Octahedral				B			Tetrahedral
		${}^3A_{2g}(F) \xrightarrow{V_1} {}^3T_{2g}(F)$	${}^3A_{2g}(F) \xrightarrow{V_2} {}^3T_{1g}(F)$	${}^3A_{2g}(F) \xrightarrow{V_3} {}^3T_{1g}(F)$	$10 Dq$	β	${}^3T_1(F) \xrightarrow{V'_1} {}^3T_1(P)$		
1	Benzene	7340	12376 (8.00)	23529 (29.00)	7340	0.89	17241 (43.00); 18692 (55.00)		
	THF	7731	12987 (9.00)	24213 (24.50)	7731	0.90	-		
	Pyridine	8053	13513 (11.50)	25062 (34.00)	8053	0.92	-		
2	Benzene	8130	13423 (10.00)	23364 (31.00)	8130	0.79	-		
	THF	8390	13850 (14.50)	24096 (28.67)	8390	0.82	-		
	Pyridine	8243	13699 (15.00)	24390 (45.00)	8243	0.85	-		
3	Benzene	7366	12391 (8.50)	23256 (25.00)	7366	0.87	17301 (24.50); 18691 (31.00)		
	Isopropyl alcohol	7724	12987 (8.67)	24330 (12.50)	7724	0.91	17006 (8.00); 19157 (11.33)		
	THF	8124	13605 (8.62)	25000 (12.50)	8124	0.91	-		
4	Pyridine	7099	12048 (11.66)	23809 (40.83)	7099	0.93	-		
	Benzene	7630	12820 (9.09)	23923 (38.64)	7630	0.89	-		
	THF	7712	12987 (9.73)	24510 (35.65)	7712	0.92	-		
5	Benzene	7228	12195 (6.67)	23255 (15.00)	7228	0.88	16949 (46.33); 18796 (50.40)		
	Isopropyl alcohol	7369	12422 (6.00)	23585 (17.50)	7369	0.90	17094 (33.00); 18975 (39.00)		
	THF	7816	13089 (7.20)	24038 (18.60)	7816	0.88	-		
6	Pyridine	7215	12225 (8.75)	23923 (18.00)	7215	0.93	-		
	Benzene	8045	13423 (8.00)	24272 (27.00)	8045	0.87	-		
	THF	7771	13021 (15.00)	23981 (30.11)	7771	0.88	-		
7	Benzene	7407	12500 (12.00)	23866 (26.00)	7407	0.90	17271 (45.00); 18518 (55.00)		
	Isopropyl alcohol	7660	12903 (9.00)	24390 (38.50)	7660	0.92	17241 (19.00); 18939 (23.50)		
	THF	7576	12788 (3.00)	24450 (33.00)	7576	0.93	-		
8	Pyridine	7136	12121 (6.00)	24096 (25.50)	7136	0.95	-		
	Benzene	7665	12804 (23.33)	23256 (63.33)	7665	0.84	-		
	THF	7746	12987 (22.50)	23981 (52.00)	7746	0.88	-		
9	Benzene	7811	13158 (11.00)	24876 (56.50)	7811	0.93	-		
	THF	7685	12987 (15.50)	25000 (56.00)	7685	0.95	-		
	Benzene	7306	12315 (11.00)	23364 (25.00)	7306	0.88	17007 (60.00); 19048 (68.00)		
10	Isopropyl alcohol	7251	12270 (7.50)	23809 (31.00)	7251	0.92	16978 (39.00); 18975 (35.00)		
	THF	7766	13003 (5.60)	23866 (21.60)	7766	0.95	-		
	Pyridine	7498	12820 (2.00)	24876 (33.00)	7498	0.96	-		
11	Benzene	7982	13351 (8.50)	24390 (37.00)	7982	0.88	-		
	THF	7573	12500 (9.00)	24038 (12.84)	7573	0.88	-		

Table-2 (contd.)

12	Benzene	7834	13141 (2.00)	24331 (16.50)	7834	931	0.89	-
	THF	7726	13021 (2.50)	24691 (21.00)	7726	969	0.93	-
13	Benzene	7404	12500 (9.50)	23923 (22.50)	7404	947	0.91	17241 (32.50); 18587 (39.50)
	Isopropyl alcohol	7515	12658 (9.00)	23981 (24.00)	7515	975	0.94	16949 (20.50); 18939 (24.50)
	THF	7618	12853 (9.50)	24510 (37.00)	7618	967	0.93	-
	Pyridine	7281	12346 (17.50)	24272 (35.50)	7281	985	0.95	-
14	Benzene	7880	13021 (9.37)	22727 (40.62)	7880	807	0.78	-
	THF	8314	13850 (9.75)	24876 (23.75)	8314	924	0.89	-
15	Benzene	7306	12315 (9.50)	23364 (25.50)	7306	917	0.88	16977 (54.00); 18867 (63.50)
	Isopropyl alcohol	7776	13072 (6.00)	24450 (31.00)	7776	946	0.91	17301 (26.50); 19305 (29.00)
	THF	7102	12048 (11.67)	23753 (40.00)	7102	966	0.93	-
	Pyridine	7816	13175 (15.00)	25000 (59.00)	7816	982	0.94	-
16	Benzene	7677	12820 (17.24)	23256 (79.31)	7677	870	0.83	-
	THF	8243	13699 (17.60)	24390 (35.00)	8243	891	0.86	-
17	Benzene	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
18	Benzene	7123	12048 (13.33)	23310 (26.67)	7123	933	0.90	17241 (70.00); 18939 (93.33)
19	Benzene	7251	12270 (18.37)	23809 (59.18)	7251	955	0.92	17182 (44.90); 18657 (55.10)

$[\{Al(OBu^t)_4\}Ni\{Zr_2(OPr^i)_9\}]^{11a}$, the chemical structural formulations for new complexes, displayed in the foregoing pages appear to be more convincing.

We wish to emphasize that, attempts to obtain X-ray crystallographically suitable crystals for these viscous or pasty or amorphous products were made, but without success. Such difficulties were frequently encountered with heterometallic alkoxide derivatives containing only alkoxo groups, not only by us, but also by other prominent workers in this field, like Bradley¹⁸ (UK), Caulton¹⁹ (USA), Pfalzgraf¹⁹ (France), Veith²⁰ (Germany).

Conclusion :

New and novel heterotrimetallic alkoxides of nickel(II) have been prepared and their physicochemical properties investigated. The new results are critically analyzed and reasonable molecular structural conclusions are drawn for the new compounds. In the near future one can expect further advances in our understanding of structural features and applications of these types of compounds.

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